

Literature review on values articulated in agrobiodiversity management

The multiple values of crop biodiversity

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1. Objectives

Numerous studies point out that biodiversity can be key to meeting challenges that modern agriculture is facing. The reasons why farmers use and maintain a diversity of seeds and crops and how they manage this biodiversity in their fields are strongly linked to farmers' values. Synthesizing the multiplicity of these values could contribute to help better target and adapt biodiversity conservation actions to local contexts, and support sustainable practices that benefit farmers, society and the environment. Here, we assess the multiple values at stake in farmers' decisions related to crop biodiversity and build a classification system of values based on farmers' local knowledge, visions, and value systems. We discuss how these values interact with local and global drivers to shape on-farm crop diversity.

2. Methods

Crops and their diversity are associated with values that have been approached in a variety of ways in the literature. As the articles do not systematically use the concept of value, we proposed to look at proxies indicating values (what people care for) and the associated valuations (the process of developing values through experience and choices made). The proxies are a set of indicators allowing to assume the existence of values and correspond to our articles search keywords (see Appendix 3). These proxies correspond to various registers of valuation (practical, rational or emotional), including preference, decision, choice, motivation, justification, attachment, utilization, judgment, consideration, effective valuation, care, perception, point of view, action, management, concern, and rationale. Valuations are the elements or qualities sought or appreciated by farmers synthesized in results 3.1.

Based on a set of 12 case studies selected from the literature, we extracted these proxies and organized them thematically in a tree of valuation processes (Appendices 1 and 2). We also extracted information about the drivers shaping local decision-making regarding crop diversity and related governance challenges.

3. Results

3.1. Valuation tree

We assessed farmers' valuations of crops and their diversity in various agricultural regions across the world (e.g. Corn Belt in the US, orchards in France, Potato Park¹ in Peru, paddy fields in Iran and Myanmar, etc.) and multiple crops (cassava, rice, walnut, wheat, etc.). The resulting valuation tree is organized in four domains. (1) The *socio-cultural domain* includes the social significance and cultural role of crops and crop diversity among various social groups. In particular, this domain encompasses the intangible dimension – that is to say the moral, spiritual and emotional aspects -- of the relationship between individual or communities and cultivated plants. For example, Angé et al. (2018) show that the concept of *respeto*, an affective and moral attitude, is central in the relationship between the Peruvian farmers of the Potato Park and the potatoes. (2) The *crop characteristics* domain relates to the morphological, physiological or phenological characteristics sought by farmers in their crops. Thant et al. (2020) showed that not only yield but resistance to harsh environmental conditions, along with cooking time, taste, aroma, and stickiness of the cooked grain, are all important values conveyed by farmers. (3) The *economic domain* refers to the financial and non-financial valuations related to the means of subsistence. These valuations are related to the needs and functioning of the rural household, including income, workload and uses of crops. For example, Nordhagen et al. (2017) show that self-sufficiency is a major value for a group of farmers in Papua New Guinea, and Mary et al. (1999) show that workload and multifunctionality are determinant in the choice of growing dual-purpose (fruits and wood) walnuts in the Dauphiné region in France. (4) The *ecological domain* includes all the ecological processes by which the crops interact with the surrounding environment (other crops, soil, pollinators, wild fauna and flora). Such interactions include the reduction of soil erosion (Mellon-Bedi et al. 2020), prevention of natural hazards (Nordhagen et al. 2017), habitat provision for wildlife (Bardsley et al. 2019) or contribution to a healthy environment (Marzban et al., 2016). This tree can be used as a tool to guide further scientific evaluations of the multiple values associated with crop diversity.

3.2. Interrelation between valuation processes in farmers' decision-making

The articles reviewed show the importance of the multiple socio-cultural, ecological, economic and agronomic valuations at stake in the decisions made by farmers regarding various levels of crop diversity, from landraces to species, and their management. Even in industrialized, low-diversity systems, farmers recognize a plurality of values in diversification (Cutforth et al. 2001). In addition, all articles reviewed point out at the various links between the domains of valuations (often all domains involved) of crops and their diversity. A visualization of the tree in the form of a Venn diagram illustrates how domains are interconnected spheres (Appendix 2). For example, in Myanmar (Thant et al., 2020), local varieties of rice are preferred not only because they have appreciated culinary qualities, but also because they are adapted to local environmental constraints such as salinity and are resistant to climatic stresses such as heavy rain. They are appreciated because of their competitiveness (high-tillering), and they are less likely to shatter or lodge; they also give high straws that are used as animal fodder. These findings highlight the need to consider values as intricate elements of a system and not as juxtapositions of individual motivations. While policies may

¹ A biocultural park dedicated to the conservation of Andean agrobiodiversity in PISAQ, near Cusco

consider farmers through the prism of economic agents, our results show that multiple levers of actions may be needed to support crop diversity.

3.3. Governance issues in crop diversity decisions: the nexus between values, power relations and global processes

Besides farmers' values, various drivers acting at different scales can influence trends in crop biodiversity. These factors can constrain the choices made by farmers beyond their own value system, but can also renew or activate existing values. The evolution of political and socio-economic contexts can indeed favor the expression of new values that become socially acceptable and admissible. It is thus important to evaluate how farmers' values interact with the evolution of economic, environmental and institutional contexts.

Global processes such as market integration are one of the factors driving a decline in the number of farmers and a homogenization of the crops grown globally (Khoury et al., 2016) but do not have the same effect at all scales (Box 2). In some systems, the promotion of improved varieties or cash crops, producing high yields under intensive and mechanized practices, have even led to sharp declines in local crop and wildlife diversity. Such promotion has led, for example, to the erosion of traditional crop diversity in the Central Himalaya -- where up to 40 species and various landraces were grown in traditional systems -- in favor of cash crops such as rice or wheat (Maikhuri et al. 1997). Other studies in the Andes (Helling and Hignman 2005) or Nepal (Upreti and Upreti 2002) show historical trends of native crop diversity erosion linked to market transformation. However, interactions between global and local forces can lead to different outcomes in farmers' fields. In particular, the mobilization of indigenous and non-indigenous knowledge, the multiple uses of crops, and organizational knowledge can all be important guarantors of maintenance of crop diversity (Zimmerer et al. 2013). For example, Brown (2013) has shown that, in the context of loss of maize genetic diversity in Mexico, local initiatives of Chiapas communities of resistance against GMOs allowed *in situ* conservation of local landraces, thanks to indigenous and scientific expertise. These initiatives organized exchanges between local farmers and set up local seed banks but also sent their seeds to other initiatives around the world. The existence of local resilience movements and institutions is essential to ensure community empowerment (Zimmerer et al., 2019, Box 1).

Labeyrie et al. (2021) reported abandonment of subsistence cereals in response to climate change and market demand; and adoption of mainly irrigated horticultural cash-crops, notably in Africa. However, changes in nutritional inputs and mismatch between climate change and crop demands may undermine future food security and farmers' capacity to adapt to climate change.

National and regional policies may also either lead to crop diversity loss, through encouraging cultivation of cash crops for exportation, as did many colonial policies (e.g. the promotion of peanut in the groundnut basin in Senegal (Lericollais 1987)) and the post-colonial "green revolution" (e.g. the promotion of agrochemical intensification of monocultures in Asia (Snapp et al. 2010)) or to the maintenance or increase in crop diversity (Zimmerer, 2013; see Box 2 for an example).

At the community scale, the articles reviewed show that decision-making is influenced by individual characteristics such as gender, education or age and thus knowledge and power relations (Mellon-Bedi et al. 2020; Mary et al. 1999). Thus, while women are at the heart of the production of certain crops, such as groundnut in Burkina Faso, they have more complex and limited access to land, tools and knowledge (Sinare et al. 2021). Crop diversity conservation is thus strongly linked to gender issues (Kerr, 2014). Household characteristics such as socio-economic status is another important local driver. For instance, Nordhagen et

al. (2018) show a diversity of profiles existing among the farmers of Papua New Guinea with, in particular, the affirmation of power linked to the possession of a great diversity of plants.

<p>Box 1. Beneficial synergies between cultural values, local organizations and national policies (Moore, 2013)</p>	<p>Box 2. Market drivers leading to the diversification of agroforestry (Michon et al. 2000)</p>
<p>Japan has experienced a considerable decrease in soybean production due to the liberalization of the market and the importation of cheaper American soybean. However, the diversity of food preparations requiring various qualities of soybeans has effectively contributed to maintain the cultivation of 59 local landraces. The production of local, diverse soybean was then supported by the confluence of two movements: (i) a growing concern of consumers for the traceability of products, which promoted the organization of direct local supply chains and labels and (ii) a support from the government for the environmental benefits linked to the national production of soybeans.</p>	<p>In a context of a lack of recognition of local communities' lands and resources by the state in Indonesia and lack of clear policy support to shifting cultivation the development of a national and international market for natural resin of a non- domesticated forest tree (<i>Shorea javanica</i>, locally damar) led to sharp changes in agroecosystems. From shifting cultivation of rainfed rice and coffee, farmers reconstituted complex agroforests through the plantation of 40 species of trees gardens becoming progressively perennial agroecosystems sustaining the existence of a large diversity of cultivated and wild species. Finally, this diversification trend allowed farmers to reclaim forest resources.</p>

4. Appendix

4.1. Appendix 1 Tree of crop / crop diversity valuation

Table of the tree of valuation. To each domain correspond one to three levels of valuation. These levels are a thematic organization of the different results from the literature. The table is read from right to left from the most general (domain) to the particular (the more precise levels of valuation). For each level one or more examples are provided.

Domain	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Examples of valuation of landraces / crops / crop diversity
1. Socio-cultural (non-material)	1.1 identity	1.1.1 individual	1.1.1.1. personal status	power, responsibility, pride, social distinction by growing rare or different crops
			1.1.1.2. attachment	
		1.1.2. group	1.1.2.1. collective identity	belonging to a group, a place, adherence to collective standards, common good (in accordance with principles), against a common opponent
			1.1.2.2. heritage	heritage, patrimony, legacy, transmission to the next generation
	1.2. sharing			cultivate for the purpose of sharing (goods or virtues) with others

	1.3. spirituality	1.3.1. rituals, ceremonial food		crops grown for special cultural events, crops with magical uses
		1.3.2. inspiration		crop that gives new sensations, fertile imagination and increased perceptions
		1.3.3. religion, prayers, intangible forces		prayers in tribute to certain crops or using certain crops for offerings / sacrifices
	1.4. aesthetic	1.4.1. beauty		visual aspect, good smell, color, shape
		1.4.2. art		seed art, leaf baskets or mats
	1.5. moral	1.5.1. humans towards non-humans		moral duty, respect, care, responsibility, stewardship, biophilia, recognition of non-humans' autonomy
		1.5.2. between humans and non-humans		interspecific reciprocity, communication, community, companionship, affect, friendship, love, kinship; biocultural wellbeing
		1.5.3. non-humans towards humans		Charisma and agency of non-humans
	1.6. knowledge	1.6.1. education, instructional tool		transmission of agricultural knowledge
		1.6.2. learning, experimental		knowledge acquired through experimentation, trial and error
1.6.3. innovation			testing new crops, discovering practices	
1.7. hobby			recreation, being outside	
2. Crop characteristics	2.1. culinary qualities / organoleptic			good taste, aroma, flavor, texture
	2.2. medicinal qualities			curing or preventing disease, active compounds, properties
	2.3. processing qualities	2.3.1. pre-processing		transformation: detoxification, milling productivity, hulling
		2.3.2. cooking		difficulty, time, techniques (steamed, boiled, baked)
	2.4. storage qualities			seed storage, post-harvest storage, in-soil storage
	2.5. agronomic	2.5.1. cycle		precocity, long cycle, short cycle
		2.5.2. adapted to local conditions	2.5.1.1. adapted to environmental	salinity, rusticity

			conditions (e.g. soils)		
			2.5.1.2. resistant to pests	resistant to insects, competitive with weeds	
			2.5.1.3. resistant to stresses or extreme events	drought	
			2.5.1.4. resistant to diseases		
		2.5.3. yields	2.5.3.1. stability		
			2.5.3.2. potential yield	high yield	
			2.5.3.3. temporal distribution		
		2.5.4. requirements	2.5.4.1 fertilizer		
			2.5.4.2. treatment (preventive or curative)	pesticides, herbicides, fungicides	
			2.5.4.3 crop assemblages, virtuous associations, rotation		
		2.5.5. growth	2.5.5.1. plant size and biomass production	tallness, branching, tillering, leaf production	
			2.5.5.2. morphological characteristics that facilitate harvesting	resistance to lodging, shattering	
			2.5.5.3. germination potential		
3. Economic	3.1. on-farm	3.1.1. own consumption	3.1.1.1 food self-sufficiency, food security		
			3.1.1.2. healthy food, nutrition		
			3.1.1.3. insurance effect	spread the risks	
		3.1.2. agricultural work	3.1.2.1. appropriate techniques and practices		
			3.1.2.2. workload, working risks		

		3.1.3. multifunctionality		several uses: attracting game, fodder, health, medicine, shelter, arcraft, energy
	3.2. economic exchanges	3.2.1. direct cash income		selling prices, fit to market demand, production costs
		3.2.2. indirect cash income		tourism
		3.2.3. incentive policies		payments for environmental services, NGO or State crop subsidies
		3.2.4. barter		
4. Ecological	4.1. soil	4.1.1 N-fixing		
		4.1.2. nutrient retention/soil fertility		
		4.1.3. soil formation/erosion		
	4.2. biotic system	4.2.1. pollination		
		4.2.2. habitat provision for wildlife		
		4.2.3. biocontrol		biological control of insects / weeds
		4.2.4. holistic interactions, (virtuous or avoidance of negative) interactions between life forms		
		4.2.5. diversity / interactions between non-humans		
		4.2.6. prevention or mitigation of natural hazards / climate change resilience		
		4.2.7. carbon sequestration		
5. Options for the future				

Tree of valuation without examples. Visualization in the form of a tree structure.

4.2. Appendix 2 Venn diagram of crop / crop diversity valuation

Domains are in bold and each domain has its own color. Crop characteristics are material valuations that are in interaction with the other domains. The different valuations (in regular writing) are distributed according to their proximity and from the most immaterial outside the figure to the most material inside the figure.

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